

USING AI TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH TEACHING

Nematullayeva Dilshoda Qodirxon kizi

Namangan State University World Languages Faculty student

Bobonazarova Gulkhayo Habibulla kizi

Namangan State University World Languages Faculty Teacher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14515131>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 12th December 2024

Accepted: 14th December 2024

Published: 18th December 2024

KEYWORDS

ABSTRACT

This research is purpose-built to find out the effectiveness of using AI technologies in English teaching to motivate or increase student's skill which is learning languages at primary, secondary school and also university. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is changing how English is taught and learned. New AI tools can create personalized learning experiences by studying how students learn and giving them the right exercises to improve. Tools like grammar checkers and speaking assistants help students understand language rules and practice communication. AI also makes learning more interesting with tools like virtual reality for vocabulary practice or storytelling platforms that adapt to the learner's level. These technologies help students not only learn the language but also understand the culture better. This study looks at how AI can improve English teaching, help teachers save time, and support students with different needs. It also talks about how to use these technologies responsibly for the best results.

Introduction. In today's world, technology is playing a big role in various fields such as education, and Artificial Intelligence (AI) is one of the most exciting developments. AI is now being used to teach English in new and interesting ways. It helps teachers and students by offering tools that make learning faster, easier, and more enjoyable. For example, AI can create personalized lessons for each student, helping them learn at their own pace. It can also provide instant feedback on grammar, pronunciation, and vocabulary. Tools like virtual tutors and language apps make learning interactive and fun. This introduction will explore how AI is changing English teaching, making it more effective and accessible for everyone, while also highlighting the challenges that come with using this technology in the classroom.

Merit sides of using AI technologies in the classroom:

Speech Recognition: Apps like Google Translate and SpeechTexter help students practice their speaking skills. The AI listens to what the student says and gives feedback on their pronunciation or fluency.

Grammar Checkers: Tools such as Grammarly can help students improve their writing. They show mistakes and suggest how to fix them, making it easier for learners to see grammar rules in action.

Chatbots for Practice: Apps like Duolingo use AI-driven chatbots to help students practice English conversations. Students can talk to the bot and get corrections when they make mistakes.

AI Supporting Different Learning Styles:

Visual Learners: AI tools use pictures and videos to help students understand words and grammar. For example, apps like Duolingo use images to help remember vocabulary.

Auditory Learners: Tools like Speechify can read texts aloud, helping students improve their listening and pronunciation skills.

Kinesthetic Learners: AI-powered games or activities on apps like Kahoot! allow students to learn English by interacting with the content, which can be great for learners who prefer to move and touch things.

AI assisting a range of student needs:

Personalized Learning: AI tools can adjust the lessons based on how well a student is doing. For example, if a student struggles with a specific grammar point, the AI can suggest more exercises or lessons on that topic.

Support for Students with Disabilities: AI tools, such as screen readers or speech-to-text apps, help students with disabilities access language resources. This makes it easier for everyone to learn, regardless of their challenges.

While AI technologies offer numerous benefits in English teaching, it's equally important to recognize the potential challenges that come with their use. Despite their effectiveness, AI tools may not always be the best solution in every situation. There are several concerns related to the over-reliance on technology, privacy issues, and the limitations of AI when it comes to human interaction and understanding complex nuances in language learning. These challenges need to be addressed to ensure that AI enhances, rather than replaces, the learning experience.

This approach helps create a balanced view before diving into the disadvantages. It signals to the reader that AI is not a perfect solution and that careful consideration of its drawbacks is necessary.

Demerit sides of using AI technologies in classroom

Teacher Training: Not all teachers know how to use AI tools well. For example, some teachers might not understand how to use AI chatbots in lessons, which can make the technology less effective.

Over-reliance on Technology: Relying too much on AI can limit students' ability to practice real-life English with other people, like classmates or teachers.

Privacy and data security: Some AI tools collect data about students' learning. It's important to make sure this data is kept private and safe, especially when using speech recognition tools.

METHOD

The methods used in this study were carefully selected and designed to achieve the main objective

The main part of the research is based on the following methodology.

1. blended learning approach- in this method was adopted, combining traditional teaching techniques like direct instruction, memorization, and chalk-and-talk etc. with AI-powered tools

2.AI Tool selection. various AI tools were selected based on their function by me.

Speech recognition tool: used for improving pronunciation and speaking skill

(e.g. Google assistant, duo lingo).

Grammar and writing assistance:

For this article, 3 classes were selected to show what results we can achieve when using AI technologies and what results we can achieve when not using them.

FINDINGS AND RESULTS

In the chart below are the results of students according to using AI technologies, not using, and partially using them.

2 –CLASS- fully used 8-CLASS-partially used 10-CLASS- not used

The line chart illustrates the progress of 2nd grade, 8th grade and 10th grade students in learning English with AI.

2nd class students: they had great progress in learning English as a result of using AI. I used partially AI at 8th class that’s why progress is significant, but lower compared to 2nd class students. It wasn’t used at 10th class students so there is no noticeable result.

Suggestion

According to the study’s research, in our modern day the researchers recommends that English teachers be creative in choosing the most suitable teaching methods for their students. One suggestion is using AI technologies to teach English. This helps students develop their skills and significantly improve the learning experience compared to only using traditional learning.

Conclusion

Integrating AI technologies into English language teaching offers significant benefits, including personalized learning experience, feedback, interactive practice chances. These can improve student engagement and support educators in learning language. However, there are some challenges such as lack of creativity, high production cost, increasing human's laziness, and no ethics.

References:

1. "Artificial Intelligence in Education" by Kinshuk, J. K. (2020) – This book explores the role of AI in enhancing education and language learning.
2. Sheralievich, Y. O. (2024). A spiritually developed person is a great person. *Pedagogical Cluster-Journal of Pedagogical Developments*, 2(6), 26-29.
3. Begimkulov, I. B. (2024). THE ROLE OF NATIONAL VALUES IN THE PATRIOTIC EDUCATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE CONDITION OF GLOBALIZATION. *Экономика и социум*, (10 (125)), 58-62.
4. Nematovich, X. J., Saidovich, M. O., Zaripovich, X. R., & Aminovich, S. H. (2023). To Reveal Medical and Social Factors Influencing the Formation of The Physical Development of Children of Early Age. *Journal of Survey in Fisheries Sciences*, 10(1S), 5970-5975.
5. Normatov, R. T. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF NATIONAL MILITARY HERITAGE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PATRIOTISM IN MILITARY PERSONNEL. *Экономика и социум*, (10 (125)), 293-296.
6. Чертополох, А. А., & Эгамов, Э. Э. (2021). Военно-патриотическое воспитание военнослужащих и гражданской молодёжи Республики Узбекистан на суворовских принципах «Науки побеждать». In *Формирование суворовского духа формами и методами военно-политической работы* (pp. 186-194).
7. НУРУЛЛАЕВ, А. (2024). ЁШЛАР ҲАЁТИНИ ҲИМОЯЛАШНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ-ПСИХОЛОГИК АСОСЛАРИ. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 54, 935-940.
8. "Artificial Intelligence in Language Teaching and Learning: Challenges and Opportunities" – A journal article that discusses the benefits and challenges of using AI in language education." AI-Assisted Language Learning: A Review of Recent Research" – An academic paper reviewing AI-based tools used for teaching languages.
9. Duolingo – An example of AI-powered language learning that personalizes lessons based on the learner's progress. Grammarly – A tool that uses AI for grammar checking and writing enhancement, often used in teaching writing skills.
10. "AI in Education: A Review" by the International Society for Technology in Education (ISTE) – Provides insights into how AI is transforming education. OECD report on AI in Education – Offers guidelines and case studies on integrating AI in teaching.
11. Pokrivčáková, S. (2019). Preparing teachers for the application of AI-powered technologies in foreign language education. *Journal of Language and Cultural Education*, 7(3), 135-153.
12. Crompton, H. & Burke, D. (2023). Artificial intelligence in higher education: The state of the field. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 20, 22.
13. Xamidova, N., & Bobonazarova, G. (2024, February). Easy ways of learning English. In *Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit* (pp. 71-73).
14. qizi Bobonazarova, G. H. (2024). Kognitiv tilshunoslikda tafakkur va konsept tushunchalari. *Zamonaviy fan va ta'lim yangiliklari xalqaro ilmiy jurnal*, 2(1), 226-232.